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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Myiasis is a parasitic infestation caused by the settlement and development of fly larvae in human or animal tissues. Although this condition is usually seen in tropical and subtropical regions, it is also reported in wider geographies due to migration, travelling and changes in hygiene conditions (Francesconi & Lupi, 2012). Myiasis cases may develop in open lesions such as wounds, ulcers, surgical sites, or rarely through larval penetration through intact skin (Robbins & Khachemoune, 2010). Diagnosis and management of myiasis cases in primary health care is often challenging. In particular, cases of myiasis developing on intact skin may be confused with cellulitis, folliculitis or other skin infections. The ability of family physicians to recognise such cases is of great importance (McGraw & Turiansky, 2008). In community-based health services, individuals' old age, poverty, lack of hygiene, underlying diseases and being in need of care also increase the risk of myiasis (Shinohara et al., 2004). This study aims to evaluate myiasis cases admitted to primary health care services within the scope of intact skin and wound infections, to define their clinical features and to contribute to family medicine practices.

Materials and Methods: Cases of intact skin and wound myiasis were evaluated from a primary care perspective; aetiology, clinical findings, diagnostic methods and management strategies were discussed in the light of the literature.

Results: Myiasis agents are generally fly species belonging to the families Calliphoridae (blowflies), Sarcophagidae (flesh flies) and Oestridae. The most frequently encountered species include *Cochliomyia hominivorax*, *Dermatobia hominis* and *Chrysomya bezziana* (McGraw & Turiansky, 2008).

Conclusion: Family physicians are the first point of contact in the diagnosis of myiasis. Early diagnosis is critical to prevent complications. Wound care and environmental hygiene are especially important in elderly, bedridden or immunocompromised individuals. Increasing the awareness of healthcare professionals working in primary care about myiasis may improve case management (Yotsu et al., 2011). Myiasis is an easily recognisable and manageable infestation that can be encountered in primary health care services, especially in developing countries. It can be prevented by hygiene, protection of open wounds and patient education. Recognition of myiasis in family medicine practices provides important gains in terms of both individual and community health.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Myiasis, tissue, human

INTRODUCTION

Myiasis is a parasitic infestation caused by the development of fly larvae within human or animal tissues. Although it is predominantly observed in tropical and subtropical regions, due to migration, travel, and changing hygiene conditions, it has also been reported in wider geographical areas (Francesconi & Lupi, 2012). Myiasis can occur in open lesions such as wounds, ulcers, or surgical sites, but it can also rarely present through larval penetration of intact skin (Robbins & Khachemoune, 2010).

Diagnosing and managing myiasis cases in primary healthcare settings can be challenging, particularly when involving intact skin, as it may be misdiagnosed as cellulitis, folliculitis, or other skin infections. Therefore, the ability of family physicians to differentiate such cases is of great importance (McGraw & Turiansky, 2008; Ockenhouse et al., 2005).

In community-based health services, factors such as aging, poverty, poor hygiene, underlying illnesses, and dependency on care also increase the risk of myiasis (Shinohara et al., 2004).

This study aims to evaluate myiasis cases presenting to primary healthcare settings in terms of intact skin and wound infections, define their clinical features, and contribute to family medicine practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Cases of intact skin and wound myiasis were evaluated from a primary care perspective; the etiology, clinical findings, diagnostic methods, and management strategies were discussed in light of the literature.

RESULTS

The causative agents of myiasis generally belong to the fly families Calliphoridae (blowflies), Sarcophagidae (flesh flies), and Oestridae. The most frequently encountered species include *Cochliomyia hominivorax*, *Dermatobia hominis*, and *Chrysomya bezziana* (McGraw & Turiansky, 2008).

Clinically, myiasis is commonly classified as follows:

- Cutaneous myiasis: A self-limiting form in which larvae penetrate intact skin.
- Wound myiasis: Characterized by larval infestation in open wounds.
- Cavitory myiasis: Larvae invade natural body cavities such as the ears, nose, or eyes.
- Gastrointestinal and urogenital myiasis: Rare forms that may develop through ingestion of contaminated food.

Patients typically present with symptoms such as pain, itching, redness, and localized inflammation. Larval movement may be felt and sometimes observed at the lesion site. In wound myiasis, foul odor, purulent discharge, and necrotic tissue are prominent findings (Yotsu et al., 2011).

Yotsu et al. (2011) described a 48-year-old male patient who presented to a rural health clinic with a painful swelling on the posterior thigh. Upon observing a central pore resembling a breathing hole with visible movement, furuncular myiasis was suspected. The larva was expelled following vaseline application. Similarly, Sharma et al. (2017) reported a diabetic 65-year-old male patient who had more than 15 larvae removed from a foul-smelling wound on the dorsum of his left foot. Robbins and Khachemoune (2010) identified myiasis in a 78-year-old bedridden female Alzheimer's patient who had developed a pressure ulcer on her sacrum. The authors emphasized the increased risk of myiasis in home care patients and the importance of caregiver education and occlusive dressings. Diagnosis of myiasis is usually made clinically; direct observation of the larva is sufficient. In some cases, imaging methods such as ultrasound or dermoscopy can also be used (Francesconi & Lupi, 2012). The primary treatment of myiasis involves the physical removal of larvae. This can be facilitated by occlusive methods (e.g., applying vaseline, ether, or oil-based dressings) to suffocate the larvae and encourage them to surface. In wound myiasis, debridement of necrotic tissue and antiseptic applications are recommended. Topical or systemic antibiotics may be necessary to prevent secondary infections (Robbins & Khachemoune, 2010).

CONCLUSION

Family physicians are often the first point of contact in diagnosing myiasis. Early diagnosis is critical in preventing complications. Ensuring proper wound care and environmental hygiene is particularly important for elderly, bedridden, or immunocompromised individuals. Increasing awareness among primary healthcare professionals about myiasis can improve case management (Gupta et al., 2014; Yotsu et al., 2011). Myiasis is an infestation that can be encountered in primary care settings, especially in developing countries, and is generally easy to recognize and manage. It is preventable through hygiene maintenance, protection of open

wounds, and patient education. Recognizing myiasis in family medicine practices yields significant benefits for both individual and public health.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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